

CALCULATING THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION FOR POWERS OF A PRIME

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Introduction

The Smarandache function is an integer function, S , of an integer variable, n . S is the smallest integer such that $S!$ is divisible by n . If the prime factorisation of n is known

$$n = \prod m_i^{p_i}$$

where the p_i are primes then it has been shown that

$$S(n) = \text{Max} \left(S(m_i^{p_i}) \right)$$

so a method of calculating S for prime powers will be useful in calculating $S(n)$.

The inverse function

It is easier to start with the inverse problem. For a given prime, p , and a given value of S , a multiple of p , what is the maximum power, m , of p which is a divisor of $S!$? If we consider the case $p=2$ then all even numbers in the factorial contribute a factor of 2, all multiples of 4 contribute another, all multiples of 8 yet another and so on.

$$m = S \text{ DIV} 2 + (S \text{ DIV} 2) \text{ DIV} 2 + ((S \text{ DIV} 2) \text{ DIV} 2) \text{ DIV} 2 + \dots$$

In the general case

$$m = S \text{ DIV} p + (S \text{ DIV} p) \text{ DIV} p + ((S \text{ DIV} p) \text{ DIV} p) \text{ DIV} p + \dots$$

The series terminates by reaching a term equal to zero. The Pascal program at the end of this paper contains a function `invSpp` to calculate this function.

Using the inverse function

If we now look at the values of S for successive powers of a prime, say $p=3$,

m	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	...
	*	*		*	*	*		*	*	*	
$S(3^m)$	3	6	9	9	12	15	18	18	21	24	...

where the asterisked values of m are those found by the inverse function, we can see that these latter determine the points after which S increases by p . In the Pascal program the procedure `tabsmarpp` fills an array with the values of S for successive powers of a prime.

The Pascal program

The program tests the procedure by accepting a prime input from the keyboard, calculating S for the first 1000 powers, reporting the time for this calculation and entering an endless loop of accepting a power value and reporting the corresponding S value as stored in the array.

The program was developed and tested with Acornsoft ISO-Pascal on a BBC Master. The function 'time' is an extension to standard Pascal which delivers the timelapse since last reset in centi-seconds. On a computer with a 65C12 processor running at 2 MHz the 1000 S values are calculated in about 11 seconds, the exact time is slightly larger for small values of the prime.

```
program TestabSpp(input,output);
var t,p,x: integer;
Smarpp:array[1..1000] of integer;

function invSpp(prime,smar:integer):integer;
var m,x:integer;
begin
m:=0;
x:=smar;
repeat
x:=x div prime;
m:=m+x;
until x<prime;
invSpp:=m;
end; {invSpp}
```

```

procedure tabsmarpp(prime,tabsize:integer);
var i,s,ls:integer;
exit:boolean;
begin
exit:=false;
i:=1;
ls:=1;
s:=prime;
repeat
repeat
Smarpp[i]:=s;
i:=i+1;
if i>tabsize then exit:=true;
until (i>ls) or exit;
s:=s+prime;
ls:=invSpp(prime,s);
until exit;
end; {tabsmarpp}

begin
read(p);
t:=time;
tabsmarpp(p,1000);
writeln((time-t)/100);
repeat
read(x);
writeln('Smarandache for ',p,' to power ',x,' is ',Smarpp[x]);
until false;
end. {testabspp}

```